

FACTORS INFLUENCING EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION IN THE CATERING DEPARTMENT OF A FIVE - STAR HOTEL IN HO CHI MINH CITY AFTER COVID-19 EPIDEMIC

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Abstract

Present circumstance although the pandemic remains complex, it has been somewhat managed and stabilized. The hotel and restaurant business has expanded. A growing move since Ho Chi Minh City is one of the main tourist destinations, and hotels need workers to get back up and operating. To be able to provide the finest experience to consumers, it is difficult to overlook the human component at restaurants, which is one of the most crucial factors. As a result, each employee is critical to the operation of the system and creating an atmosphere in which employees are happy can increase job quality and employee performance. The goal is to identify and evaluate the factors influencing customer satisfaction of food and beverage department staff after opening reopening due to the Covid-19 epidemic situation, thereby offering solutions to promote strengths and overcome weaknesses to help the Food and Beverage (F&B) department perform better, increase employee satisfaction with the business, and that is also the premise to help increase employee productivity and efficiency. In the current age, this study report highlights the aspects influencing employee happiness such as salaries, workplace culture, training system, co-workers, and significantly gender equality. Research contributes to the partial solution of the human resource problem, which is the foundation for delivering answers to work inspiration as well as contemporary labor challenges.

Keywords: restaurant, food, beverage, business, motivation

Introduction

The difficulty of enterprise disruption and severe labor shortages as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic's transfer of workforce from the city to the rural. Because of this scarcity, many organizations are forced to advertise recruitment in order to restore production and business, paying significant expenditures associated with recruiting and training new personnel, as well as requiring extra time to raise quality. Labor relations and business culture are both being built. The problem of unacceptable labor resource quality owing to low skills and a lack of soft skills should have a significant impact on firm output and profitability. Employees' degree of adaptability to the speed with which new working techniques and models are being updated. This lack of skill makes it difficult for employees to keep up with the enterprise's innovation speed, resulting in a "phase difference" that slows the company recovery process. The impact of the Covid-19 epidemic on employees' physical and mental health decreases their productivity and organizational performance (research on the impact of COVID-19 pandemic). Investing in Women (IW) and VBCWE are spreading the Covid-19 epidemic to Vietnamese private sector employees. Faced with these issues, firms prioritize the strategy of simultaneously revitalizing and consolidating human resources. So, what challenges should company leaders focus on in order to boost labor capacity, which is a crucial driving force for

post-pandemic development and recovery, as well as investigate the elements influencing satisfaction in order to find the best solutions. Per the Resolution 11/NQ-CP, the number of workers working at firms in the first quarter of 2022 has grown compared to the fourth quarter of 2021 under the program of socioeconomic recovery and development. As a result, the number of personnel In the first quarter of 2022, there were around 1.3 million unemployed persons, a decrease of 135.2 thousand from the previous quarter and an increase of 357.5 thousand from the same period last year. In the first quarter of 2022, the underemployment rate of working-age workers was 3.01 percent, down 0.36 percentage points from the previous quarter but up 0.81 percentage points from the same period last year. Underemployment among working-age people is lower in cities than in rural regions (2.39 percent and 3.40 percent respectively). In terms of income, the average monthly income of employees increased significantly in most key economic sectors in the first quarter of 2022 as compared to the previous quarter. Employees' average monthly income in the first quarter was 6.4 million VND, a 1 million VND rise over the previous quarter and a 110,000 VND gain over the same period last year. Male employees' average monthly salary is 1.36 times greater than female workers' average monthly income (7.3 million VND compared to 5.4 million VND). The average wage in urban regions is 1.43 times that of rural ones (7.9 million VND compared to 5.5 million VND). The data above illustrate that the job market in 2022 has thrived, however there are other difficulties to be concerned about. Enterprises tend to tighten their needs as well as how to recruit employees when reorganizing production and business, because they recognize the importance of workers needing proficiency in information technology skills, technical skills, flexibility, and the ability to adapt to unexpected changes in the environment.

Literature review

Many research, both domestic and international, have presented the overall notion of job satisfaction in a variety of ways. As a result, below is the definition of employee satisfaction. Motivation may also be interpreted in a variety of ways. Landsberger (1958) popularized the notion as the "Hawthorne Effect." Although the author did not update the work satisfaction idea in research, it is regarded as the cornerstone of job satisfaction development. Job satisfaction, according to Maslow (1943), is still excellent research as fulfilment of individual needs and goals. Employee satisfaction is defined by Locke (1976) as a cheerful or positive emotional state resulting from job appraisal or work experience. Herzberg (1968) and Alderfer (1969) argued that employee satisfaction is all about job satisfaction or the employee's effort to maintain employment is demonstrated by the perception (positive or negative) poles, or a combination of both, about different aspects of your work that affect your surname. The JDI (Work Descriptive Index) model, often known as the job description scale, is a frequently used measure of job satisfaction. This measurement was developed by Smith, Kendall, and Hulin and originally published in the book "Measurement" in 1969. The Job Description Index, which employs 72 measurement questions, assesses employee job satisfaction in five areas. JDI's value and dependability are well regarded in both practice and theory, with JDI being used in more than half of all research publications published. As a result, there are several definitions of employee satisfaction movements. As a result, the employee's level of pleasure or

unhappiness with the job is constantly vary based on the many assessment criteria. It is possible to conclude that Satisfaction

Employees' hearts are in a condition of joy, comfort, and expressiveness when they respond positively to components of their work.

Research Methodology

Secondary data was gathered from a variety of sources, including books, publications, past study subjects, and concerns relevant to the topic. The focus group discussion approach allows members to openly voice their thoughts and contradict earlier perspectives. These thoughts are expressed in writing and agreed upon by a majority. The outcomes of this debate will be used to confirm the model's accuracy and to develop formal scales for the survey. The focus group comprises of five people (02 lecturers and 03 F&B experts). Quantitative technique of data collecting via survey distribution the personnel in the F&B department then evaluate the data collected using SPSS software version 20.0. The sample size should be greater than 100 and the smallest sample should have the desired ratio of 5 observations for each variable. To ensure a sample size of 100 increase 30% of the minimum sample size because during data collection will have to remove unsatisfactory questionnaires.

Research result and discussion

Table 1: The general information of the respondents

Demographic		Quantity	(%)
Gender	Male	150	60
	Female	100	40
Age	From 25 to 35 years old	200	80
	From 35 to 45 years old	50	20
Income	<25 million	180	72
	From 25 to 35 million	50	20
	>35 million	20	8
Total		250	100

According to the (Table 1) men accounting for 60% of all people, while female customers accounting for 40% (100 persons). The age group from 25 to 35 years old makes for the majority (80%), followed by the age group from 35 to 45 years old (20%). According to the results of this poll, less than 25 million people witnessed 180 surveys (72 percent). The next 20 percent is from 25 to 35 million, and the last is beyond 35 million (8 percent).

TABLE 2: Cronbach's alpha values for each of the compound variables

Factor	Number of variables observe	Cronbach's Alpha	Coefficient minimum total variable correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if the variable type is smallest value	Conclusion
Salary	5	0.891	0.787	0.881	Qualified
Gender equality	5	0.857	0.854	0.815	Qualified
Environment	5	0.765	0.712	0.857	Qualified
Training program	5	0.729	0.743	0.821	Qualified
Co-workers	5	0.767	0.761	0.857	Qualified
Satisfaction	5	0.829	0.735	0.852	Qualified

The scale is good if the Cronbach coefficient is from 0.7 to 0.8. Furthermore, the variables' least adjusted item-total correlation is greater than 0.4, and Cronbach's Alpha is greater than 0.6 if the item is omitted, indicating that the reliability of all variables is good (Table 2).

Table 3: Cronbach's Alpha reliability test results and KMO

Factor	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
MN1	15.69	5.645	.763
MN2	15.38	6.650	.661
MN3	15.65	5.692	.647
MN4	15.60	5.458	.658
MN5	15.71	7.617	.738
CW1	16.84	6.269	.721
CW2	16.50	6.889	.713
CW3	16.84	6.701	.715
CW4	16.10	6.582	.741
CW5	16.75	6.479	.718
EV1	15.01	7.507	.594
EV2	17.30	7.598	.696
EV3	17.10	6.513	.765
EV4	17.27	7.582	.790
EV5	17.83	7.559	.604
TP1	17.51	6.757	.639
TP2	17.54	6.643	.616
TP3	17.41	6.283	.719
TP4	17.73	7.397	.637
TP5	17.46	7.341	.765
GE1	16.22	7.498	.596
GE2	16.10	6.513	.865
GE3	16.27	6.682	.890
GE4	16.33	7.659	.804
GE5	16.11	6.757	.839

The variables have a Cronbach's alpha value larger than 0.6 less than 0.99 and a variable correlation coefficient better than 0.4 overall, according to the data. These variables will be utilized in the EFA analysis that follows. Analyzing EFA factors will reveal if the aforesaid scales are divided into new or deleted components with more precision. According to the writers Hoang and Chu (2008): First, the KMO coefficient is 0.50, and the Bartlett's test significance

level is 0.50. Second, factor loading 0.50, an observed variable is deleted if its loading factor is less than 0.50.

Third, the measure is acceptable if the total variance retrieved exceeds 50%. Fourth, the number of factors is calculated using the eigenvalue coefficient, which indicates the explained spread for each component and must have a value of 1. Fifth, until a discriminant value between factors is achieved, the difference in a load factor of an observed variable among factors is 0.30.

Table 4: KMO and Bartlett's

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.874	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1872.766
	Df	175
	Sig.	.000

After examining Cronbach's Alpha, valid scales will be included in the next assessment using EFA exploratory factor analysis. The factor analysis approach requires that the KMO be more than 0.6 Garson, (2003), and the significance threshold be sig 0.05. The Bartlett test results reveal that it passes the conditions for running EFA with a sig. of 0.000 0.05 and a KMO > 0.5, showing that the conceptual validity test of the scale is adequate for analysis. accumulate.

Table 5: Factor loading of independent variables

Factors	Component					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
MN1	.821					
MN2	.818					
MN3	.880					
MN4	.753					
MN5	.721					
CW1		.783				
CW2		.788				
CW3		.776				
CW4		.742				
CW5		.701				
EV1			.864			
EV2			.846			
EV3			.805			
EV4			.898			
EV5			.892			
IN1				.726		
IN2				.715		
IN3				.791		
IN4				.719		
IN5				.729		
GE1					.633	
GE2					.645	
GE3					.676	
GE4					.698	
GE5					.688	
SP1						.707
SP2						.797
SP3						.769
SP4						.748
SP5						.722

The factor rotation matrix table demonstrates that the observed variables' factor loading coefficients are all greater than 0.6. The scale has excellent reliability and is utilized for

regression analysis to quantify the influence of independent factors on satisfaction. As a result, the scale of factors impacting the extracted components is both trustworthy and valid. The scales are suitable for hypotheses testing.

Table 6: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.825 ^a	.626	.628	.35120	1.932

The regression analysis findings reveal that adjusted R² = 0.628, indicating that the independent variable impacts 62.8 percent of the change in the dependent variable when conducting the regression analysis. Durbin-Watson coefficient = 1.932, in the range of 1.5 to 2.5, indicating that no autocorrelation exists.

Table 6: synthesis analysis ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	29.358	6	58.796	155,112	0,000
Residual	36.518	273			
Total	65.876	268			

The model fit test results are shown in Table 6 with the Sig value of 0.00 0.05 and the statistic F = 155.112, proving that the theoretical model is consistent with reality and that the independent variables have a linear relationship with the dependent variable and that the multiple linear regression model fits the data set and can be used.

Recommendation

One of the process parameters influencing employee satisfaction working in such department is about training and advancement. Despite recent changes in the training system and promotion route for employees, the F&B department has not yet attained efficiency, which impacts employee satisfaction with the job and the department's performance. Because the nature of the job affects satisfaction, all levels are affected. Soon, steps must be taken to strengthen the F&B sector. Improve employee work-related issues and duties as follows to meet the nature of the job, the entire department must study and execute the development of descriptions for each position and title. Create a comfortable working atmosphere among employees, have frequent open meetings with employees so that they better understand each other, work together better, and know how to care for and share with one another, so that the job is better for all employees.

Everyone understands the significance of their contribution to the department, and the cultural climate mutual trust is established by listening to one another and offering constructive suggestions in order to progress together. Create a pleasant working environment for workers and hold frequent open meetings with them so that they properly appreciate each other, work better together, and know how to care for something and share with one another, making the job easier for everyone. Everyone recognizes the importance of their participation to the

business, and the cultural atmosphere fosters mutual trust by listening to one another and making helpful comments in order to improve together.

Businesses must provide a safe and professional workplace with appropriate working conditions in order to retain personnel. Aside from wage and bonus considerations, executives must also consider trust building and sharing, wellness and mental health benefits, business culture, and fundamental values. The core attracts and engages the team. Building a broad, egalitarian, and inclusive cultural backdrop that respects gender and regional variations is critical for organizations to retain and assure employee happiness. Concentrate on the most vulnerable populations According to the study report, Covid-19 impacts female employees more than male workers since women carry higher duties in caring for the family and must spend more time with them. housework. As a result, authorities must pay more attention to both the emotional and physical health of this more vulnerable demographic, including policies that strengthen women's rights and emphasize equal values in the community. enterprise. Gender equality in the workplace does not imply that the number of men and women in the organization must be balanced; rather, it implies that everyone has equal access to the same opportunities and resources and is compensated equally. comparable employment, regardless of gender Gender equality is the removal of impediments to women's full and equal involvement in the workforce; it is non-discriminatory in any profession, including leadership positions; and it is to remove sex discrimination, particularly in topics relating to the family and family care obligations. Gender equality benefits employee happiness, team cohesiveness, and the ability to recruit, develop, and retain talent. Gender equality and diversity and inclusion (D&I) are especially important to the youthful workforce (Millennials and Generation Z), and are increasingly being addressed while choosing a job.

Conclusion

The study sheds light on the concept and methods of gauging employee job satisfaction. gather, evaluate, and form preliminary conclusions on the degree of satisfaction of workers working in the F&B department Labor has been used to build and test the suggested test model and assumptions. Initially, a scale of influencing variables and employee satisfaction was developed. Some suggestions for ensuring and maintaining long-term employee happiness in the future.

Conflict of interests

None

References

1. Ibrahim, I. (2021). Factors Effecting Employees Retention in The Malaysian Manufacturing Industry During the Pandemic Covid-19: The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction. *Asian Journal of Research in Business and Management*, 3(3), 24-39.
2. Jiony, M. M., Lew, T. Y., Gom, D., Tanakinjal, G. H., & Sondoh Jr, S. (2021). Influence of cultural intelligence and psychological capital on service quality: A study of the hotel industry in Sabah, Malaysia. *Sustainability*, 13(19), 10809.

3. Njuki, J., Eissler, S., Malapit, H., Meinzen-Dick, R., Bryan, E., & Quisumbing, A. (2022). A review of evidence on gender equality, women's empowerment, and food systems. *Global Food Security*, 33, 100622.
4. Chang, E. H., & Milkman, K. L. (2020). Improving decisions that affect gender equality in the workplace. *Organizational Dynamics*, 49(1), 100709.
5. García Johnson, C. P., & Otto, K. (2019). Better together: A model for women and LGBTQ equality in the workplace. *Frontiers in psychology*, 10, 272.
6. Moser, C. E., & Branscombe, N. R. (2022). Male allies at work: gender-equality supportive men reduce negative underrepresentation effects among women. *Social Psychological and Personality Science*, 13(2), 372-381.
7. Alrawadieh, Z., Demirdelen Alrawadieh, D., Olya, H. G., Erkol Bayram, G., & Kahraman, O. C. (2022). Sexual harassment, psychological well-being, and job satisfaction of female tour guides: The effects of social and organizational support. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 30(7), 1639-1657.
8. Salem, I. E., Elkhwesky, Z., & Ramkissoon, H. (2022). A content analysis for government's and hotels' response to COVID-19 pandemic in Egypt. *Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 22(1), 42-59.
9. Leung, V. T., & Lin, P. M. (2022). The roles of multiple foci of employee commitments and job satisfaction on creative performance: a study of hotel chefs. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 101, 103107.
10. Wu, C., Layraman, T., & Huang, C. (2022). Study of M Hotel Staff's Relationship Between Job Satisfaction and Loyalty. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 4684-4693.